

Clinicopathological Correlations in Immunoglobulin a Nephropathy (IgAN) According to the Oxford MEST-C Classification: A single-Center Study in Karbala

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Immunoglobulin A nephropathy (IgAN) is the most common primary glomerulonephritis worldwide and an important cause of chronic kidney disease and kidney failure. The disease demonstrates heterogeneous clinical and histopathological features, making clinicopathological correlation essential for prognostic evaluation.

Objective: To evaluate the relationship between biochemical parameters and histopathological findings in IgAN according to the Oxford MEST-C classification.

Methods: This retrospective cross-sectional study included 55 patients diagnosed with IgAN at Al-Kafeel Hospital and Al-Kafeel Center for Kidney Diseases and Transplantation in Karbala, Iraq, between January 2017 and August 2025. Clinical, biochemical, histopathological, and immunofluorescence data were reviewed. Renal biopsies were assessed using the Oxford MEST-C classification and immunofluorescence staining. Associations between laboratory findings and histopathological parameters were analyzed statistically.

Results: Microscopic hematuria was present in 94.4% of patients, while proteinuria (+1) was the most frequent grade (32.7%). Oxford classification showed predominance of M0 (74.5%), E0 (50.9%), S0 (52.7%), T0 (83.6%), and C1 (47.3%). Median blood urea and serum creatinine were significantly higher in patients with advanced segmental sclerosis, tubular atrophy/interstitial fibrosis, and crescents. No significant association was found between sex, hematuria, or proteinuria and MEST-C scores ($p > 0.05$). Immunofluorescence revealed significant positive correlations between IgA and both C1q and C3, with a

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stronger correlation between IgA and IgG. Positive C3, IgM, and IgG deposits were associated with significantly higher urea and creatinine levels, indicating impaired renal function.

Conclusions: Biochemical markers, particularly serum creatinine and blood urea, are significantly associated with histopathological severity in IgAN. Combined immune deposits, especially C3, IgM, and IgG, may indicate worse renal impairment and disease progression.

Keywords: Clinicopathological, Immunoglobulin A Nephropathy, Oxford MEST-C.

INTRODUCTION:

IgA nephropathy (IgAN) is the most common primary glomerulonephritis worldwide and remains a major cause of chronic kidney disease (CKD) and end-stage renal disease (ESRD) in both developed and developing countries^(1,2). It was first described by Berger and Hinglais in 1968 and is characterized by dominant or co-dominant mesangial deposition of immunoglobulin A (IgA)-containing immune complexes within the glomeruli, leading to progressive glomerular injury and renal dysfunction⁽²⁾. The prevalence of IgAN varies considerably among different populations, with the highest incidence reported in East Asia compared with Europe and North America^(3,4). This geographical variability may be related to genetic susceptibility, environmental influences, screening strategies, biopsy policies, and accessibility of immunofluorescence microscopy⁽⁵⁾. Clinically, IgAN demonstrates a highly heterogeneous presentation. Patients may present with recurrent episodes of gross hematuria, usually following upper respiratory tract infections, microscopic hematuria, proteinuria, nephrotic syndrome, or rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis^(5,6).

Although the disease commonly affects young adults, the age at diagnosis has increased in recent years. Male predominance is frequently reported, and disease severity may differ according to age and associated comorbidities⁽⁷⁾. Histopathologically, IgAN is characterized by mesangial proliferation, extracellular matrix expansion, and deposition of IgA with complement component C3, while IgG and IgM co-deposition

may also occur in some cases^(8,9). Activation of complement pathways and immune complex formation are considered important mechanisms contributing to glomerular inflammation and progressive renal damage⁽¹⁰⁾.

Because the clinical course of IgAN ranges from benign disease to progressive renal failure, accurate prognostic evaluation is essential. Clinical risk factors associated with poor renal outcome include persistent proteinuria, hypertension, impaired glomerular filtration rate, and advanced age at presentation⁽¹¹⁾. However, histopathological assessment obtained from renal biopsy has become increasingly important in predicting disease progression and guiding therapeutic decisions^(12,13).

To standardize pathological evaluation, the Oxford Classification was introduced in 2009 by the International IgA Nephropathy Network and the Renal Pathology Society, and later updated in 2017^(14,15). The classification assesses mesangial hypercellularity (M), endocapillary hypercellularity (E), segmental glomerulosclerosis (S), tubular atrophy/interstitial fibrosis (T), and crescents (C), collectively known as the MEST-C score. Multiple studies have validated the prognostic significance of these lesions in predicting renal outcome and disease progression⁽¹⁶⁾. Recent evidence suggests that integrating histopathological findings with biochemical and immunological markers may improve prediction of renal prognosis in IgAN patients. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate clinicopathological correlations in IgAN by linking biochemical parameters with histopathological

findings according to the Oxford MEST-C classification.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

This retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted in the pathology departments of Al-Kafeel Hospital and Al-Kafeel Center for Kidney Diseases and Transplantation in Karbala City, Iraq, during the period from January 2017 to August 2025. The study included archival cases diagnosed with IgA nephropathy (IgAN). A total of 55 renal biopsy histopathology reports were collected and reviewed according to the study inclusion and exclusion criteria. Demographic, clinical, laboratory, and histopathological data were retrospectively obtained from patients' medical records. No prospective follow-up was performed, as the study relied exclusively on previously documented data.

Inclusion criteria comprised all patients with a confirmed diagnosis of IgAN and complete clinical and laboratory information, including hematuria, proteinuria, serum creatinine, blood urea, and complete histopathological reports. Secondary causes of IgA deposition, including hepatic, gastrointestinal, infectious, rheumatologic, neoplastic, dermatological, and other systemic diseases, were excluded after review of the patients' records. Cases with incomplete clinical or histopathological information, including inadequate immunofluorescence evaluation, were excluded from the study. Kidney biopsy specimens were obtained under ultrasound guidance. Three renal tissue cores were collected from each patient. Two cores were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for routine histopathological examination, while

the third core was kept fresh and snap-frozen for immunofluorescence studies. Histological sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin, periodic acid–Schiff, Masson's trichrome, Jones' methenamine silver, and Congo red stains. Biopsy specimens were required to contain at least 4–8 glomeruli for light microscopy and 2–4 glomeruli for immunofluorescence evaluation. Histopathological assessment was performed by a single pathologist. Immunofluorescence studies assessed IgA, IgG, IgM, C3, and C1q deposits using fluorescence microscopy with FITC filters. Images were captured using an Olympus DP72 microscope camera. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 24.0. Frequencies, percentages, mean \pm standard deviation, median, and interquartile range were used for data presentation. Chi-square test, Mann–Whitney U test, and Kruskal–Wallis test were applied as appropriate. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULT:

The study included 55 patients. Regarding sex distribution, females accounted for 27 (49.1%), while males accounted for 28 (50.9%), indicating a near-equal representation of both sexes in the study sample. According to age groups, patients were classified into four categories. The 27–42 years' age group represented the largest proportion of the sample, comprising 25 patients (45.5%), followed by the 11–26 years' age group with 22 patients (40.0%). The 43–58 years' age group included 6 patients (10.9%), whereas the 59–72 years' age group was the least represented, with only 2 patients (3.6%). The mean age of the sample was 31.98 ± 13.29 years, as presented in table (1).

Table (1): Demographic data of patients (N = 55)

Variable	Category	N	%
Sex	Female	27	49.1
	Male	28	50.9
Age group (years)	11–26yrs	22	40.0
	27–42yrs	25	45.5
	43–58yrs	6	10.9
	59–72yrs	2	3.6
Age (mean ± SD) (range)	31.98±13.29 (11-72)		
Total	—	55	100.0

Regarding MEST-C classification, 74.5% had (M0) mesangial cellularity, 50.9% had endocapillary hypercellularity (E0), 52.7% had segmental sclerosis (S0), 83.6% had (T0) interstitial

fibrosis/tubular atrophy and 47.3% had (C1) cellular or fibrocellular crescents, as presented in table (2).

Table (2): Distribution of MEST-C classification

	Parameter	Category	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
MEST-C classification	Mesangial cellularity (M)	M0	41	74.5
		M1	14	25.5
	Endocapillary hypercellularity (E)	E0	28	50.9
		E1	27	49.1
	Segmental sclerosis (S)	S0	29	52.7
		S1	26	47.3
		Interstitial fibrosis/tubular atrophy (T)	T0	46
		T1	9	16.4
		T2	0	0.0
	Cellular or fibrocellular crescents (C)	C0	25	45.5
		C1	26	47.3
		C2	4	7.3
Total	—	55	100.0	

Estimation of other parameters showed that hematuria was observed in 52 (94.5%) cases as microscopic, while macroscopic hematuria was observed in 3 (5.5%) cases. Additionally, among

the patients, a positive family history was reported in 2 (3.6%) cases, and a history of chronic kidney disease (CKD) was reported in 7 (12.7%) cases as presented in table (3).

Table (3): Clinical Characteristics of the Study Patients

Parameter	Category	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Hematuria	Microscopic	52	94.5
	Macroscopic	3	5.5
Family history	Positive	2	3.6
History of CKD	Present	7	12.7
Total	—	55	100.0

No statistical significant association between sex of patients with hematuria, proteinuria, mesangial cellularity, endocapillary hypercellularity, segmental sclerosis, interstitial fibrosis/tubular atrophy, cellular or fibrocellular crescents, C1q,

C3, Ig G, Ig A, Ig M, family history and history of CKD (p 0.611, 0.141, 0.068, 0.79, 0.422, 0.142, 0.11, 0.611, 0.31, 0.705, 0.076, 0.474, 1.00 and 1.00, respectively), as presented in table (4).

Table (4): Association of Patient Sex with Clinical, Histopathological, and Immunofluorescence Findings.

		Sex		Total	P-value
		Female	Male		
Hematuria	microscopic	25(48.1%)	27(51.9%)	52(100.0%)	0.611
	macroscopic	2(66.7%)	1(33.3%)	3(100.0%)	
protein urea(mg/dl)	Negative (<10mg/dl)	2(40.0%)	3(60.0%)	5(100.0%)	0.141
	+1 (30mg/dl)	6(33.3%)	12(66.7%)	18(100.0%)	
	+2 (100mg/dl)	5(41.7%)	7(58.3%)	12(100.0%)	
	+3 (300mg/dl)	2(40.0%)	3(60.0%)	5(100.0%)	
	+4(>1000mg/dl)	1(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	1(100%)	
	Trace (15mg/dl)	11(78.6%)	3(21.4%)	14(100%)	
Mesangial cellularity (M)	M0	17(41.5%)	24(58.5%)	41(100%)	0.068
	M1	10(71.4%)	4(28.6%)	14(100%)	
Endocapillary hypercellularity (E)	E0	13(46.4%)	15(53.6%)	28(100%)	0.79
	E1	14(51.9%)	13(48.1%)	27(100%)	
Segmental sclerosis (S)	S0	16(55.2%)	13(44.8%)	29(100%)	0.422
	S1	11(42.3%)	15(57.7%)	26(100.0%)	
Interstitial fibrosis/tubular atrophy (T)	T0	25(54.3%)	21(45.7%)	46(100.0%)	0.142
	T1	2(22.2%)	7(77.8%)	9(100.0%)	

	T2	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	
Cellular or fibrocellular crescents (C)	C0	16(64.0%)	9(36.0%)	25(100.0%)	0.11
	C1	10(38.5%)	16(61.5%)	26(100.0%)	
	C2	1(25.0%)	3(75.0%)	4(100.0%)	
C1q	0	26(50.0%)	26(50.0%)	52(100.0%)	0.611
	+1	1(50.0%)	1(50.0%)	2(100.0%)	
	+2	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	
	+3	0(0.0%)	1(100.0%)	1(100.0%)	
C3	0	19(57.6%)	14(42.4%)	33(100.0%)	0.311
	+1	3(42.9%)	4(57.1%)	7(100.0%)	
	+2	5(38.5%)	8(61.5%)	13(100.0%)	
	+3	0(0.0%)	2(100.0%)	2(100.0%)	
IgG	0	18(52.9%)	16(47.1%)	34(100.0%)	0.705
	+1	6(40.0%)	9(60.0%)	15(100.0%)	
	+2	3(50.0%)	3(50.0%)	6(100.0%)	
	+3	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	
IgA	0	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0.076
	+1	11(68.8%)	5(31.3%)	16(100.0%)	
	+2	14(46.7%)	16(53.3%)	30(100.0%)	
	+3	2(22.2%)	7(77.8%)	9(100.0%)	
IgM	0	13(48.1%)	14(51.9%)	27(100.0%)	0.474
	+1	11(57.9%)	8(42.1%)	19(100.0%)	
	+2	3(33.3%)	6(66.7%)	9(100.0%)	
	+3	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	
family history	Negative	26(49.1%)	27(50.9%)	53(100.0%)	1.00
	Positive	1(50.0%)	1(50.0%)	2(100.0%)	
history of CKD	Negative	24(50.0%)	24(50.0%)	48(100.0%)	1.00
	Positive	3(42.9%)	4(57.1%)	7(100.0%)	
Total		27(49.1%)	28(50.9%)	55(100.0%)	

No statistically significant association between type of hematuria with MEST-C classification and Immunofluorescences examination (p 1.00, 0.61,

1.00, 1.00, 0.746, 0.913, 0.642, 0.383, 0.657 and 0.698, respectively), as presented in table (5).

Table (5): Association between type of hematuria with MEST-C classification and Immunofluorescences examination.

	Hematuria			Total	P-value
	m	microscopic	macroscopic		
Mesangial cellularity (M)	M0	39(95.1%)	2(4.9%)	41(100.0%)	1.00
	M1	13(92.9%)	1(7.1%)	14(100.0%)	
Endocapillary hypercellularity (E)	E0	27(96.4%)	1(3.6%)	28(100.0%)	0.61
	E1	25(92.6%)	2(7.4%)	27(100.0%)	
Segmental sclerosis (S)	S0	27(93.1%)	2(6.9%)	29(100.0%)	1.00
	S1	25(96.2%)	1(3.8%)	26(100.0%)	
Interstitial fibrosis/tubular atrophy (T)	T0	43(93.5%)	3(6.5%)	46(100.0%)	1.00
	T1	9(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	9(100.0%)	
	T2	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	
Cellular or fibrocellular crescents (C)	C0	24(96.0%)	1(4.0%)	25(100.0%)	0.746
	C1	24(92.3%)	2(7.7%)	26(100.0%)	
	C2	4(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	4(100.0%)	
C1q	0	49(94.2%)	3(5.8%)	52(100.0%)	0.913
	+1	2(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(100.0%)	
	+2	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	
	+3	1(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	1(100.0%)	
C3	0	32(97.0%)	1(3.0%)	33(100.0%)	0.642
	+1	6(85.7%)	1(14.3%)	7(100.0%)	
	+2	12(92.3%)	1(7.7%)	13(100.0%)	
	+3	2(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(100.0%)	
IgG	0	33(97.1%)	1(2.9%)	34(100.0%)	0.383
	+1	14(93.3%)	1(6.7%)	15(100.0%)	
	+2	5(83.3%)	1(16.7%)	6(100.0%)	
	+3	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	
IgA	0	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0.657
	+1	15(93.8%)	1(6.3%)	16(100.0%)	
	+2	29(96.7%)	1(3.3%)	30(100.0%)	
	+3	8(88.9%)	1(11.1%)	9(100.0%)	
IgM	0	25(92.6%)	2(7.4%)	27(100.0%)	0.698
	+1	18(94.7%)	1(5.3%)	19(100.0%)	
	+2	9(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	9(100.0%)	
	+3	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	
Total		52(94.5%)	3(5.5%)	55(100.0%)	

No statistically significant association between proteinuria with MEST-C classification and Immunofluorescences examination (p 0.253, 0.314,

0.669, 0.659, 0.578, 0.258, 0.853, 0.677, 0.606, 0.425 and 0.774, respectively), as presented in table (6).

Table (6): Association between proteinuria with MEST-C classification and Immunofluorescences examination.

		Proteinuria		Total	P-value
		Negative	Positive		
Hematuria	Microscopic	4(7.7%)	48(92.3%)	52(100.0%)	0.253
	Macroscopic	1(33.3%)	2(66.7%)	3(100.0%)	
Mesangial cellularity (M)	M0	5(12.2%)	36(87.8%)	41(100.0%)	0.314
	M1	0(0.0%)	14(100.0%)	14(100.0%)	
Endocapillary hypercellularity (E)	E0	2(7.1%)	26(92.9%)	28(100.0%)	0.669
	E1	3(11.1%)	24(88.9%)	27(100.0%)	
Segmental sclerosis (S)	S0	2(6.9%)	27(93.1%)	29(100.0%)	0.659
	S1	3(11.5%)	23(88.5%)	26(100.0%)	
Interstitial fibrosis/tubular atrophy (T)	T0	5(10.9%)	41(89.1%)	46(100.0%)	0.578
	T1	0(0.0%)	9(100.0%)	9(100.0%)	
	T2	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	
Cellular or fibrocellular crescents (C)	C0	4(16.0%)	21(84.0%)	25(100.0%)	0.258
	C1	1(3.8%)	25(96.2%)	26(100.0%)	
	C2	0(0.0%)	4(100.0%)	4(100.0%)	
C1q	0	5(9.6%)	47(90.4%)	52(100.0%)	0.853
	+1	0(0.0%)	2(100.0%)	2(100.0%)	
	+2	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	
	+3	0(0.0%)	1(100.0%)	1(100.0%)	
C3	0	3(9.1%)	30(90.9%)	33(100.0%)	0.677
	+1	0(0.0%)	7(100.0%)	7(100.0%)	
	+2	2(15.4%)	11(84.6%)	13(100.0%)	
	+3	0(0.0%)	2(100.0%)	2(100.0%)	
IgG	0	4(11.8%)	30(88.2%)	34(100.0%)	0.606
	+1	1(6.7%)	14(93.3%)	15(100.0%)	
	+2	0(0.0%)	6(100.0%)	6(100.0%)	
	+3	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	
IgA	0	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0.425
	+1	1(6.3%)	15(93.8%)	16(100.0%)	
	+2	4(13.3%)	26(86.7%)	30(100.0%)	
	+3	0(0.0%)	9(100.0%)	9(100.0%)	
IgM	0	3(11.1%)	24(88.9%)	27(100.0%)	0.774
	+1	1(5.3%)	18(94.7%)	19(100.0%)	
	+2	1(11.1%)	8(88.9%)	9(100.0%)	
	+3	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	
Total		5(9.1%)	50(90.9%)	55(100.0%)	

Median blood urea levels showed statistically significant differences according to segmental sclerosis, interstitial fibrosis/tubular atrophy, and crescent formation. Higher median blood urea levels (25th–75th percentile) were observed in patients with S1 compared with S0 lesions [28.50 (10.92–53.75) vs 12.40 (9.35–18.00), $p=0.014$], T1 compared with T0 lesions [52.00 (23.70–74.00) vs 9.97 (9.97–28.25), $p=0.008$], and C2 compared with C1 and C0 lesions [72.00 (35.50–104.75) vs 21.20 (10.90–49.00) vs 11.40 (8.75–16.60), $p=0.002$], respectively. Similarly, median serum creatinine levels differed significantly according to

segmental sclerosis, interstitial fibrosis/tubular atrophy, and crescent scores. Patients with S1 lesions had significantly higher serum creatinine levels than those with S0 lesions [1.04 (0.77–4.08) vs 0.81 (0.68–0.99), $p=0.019$]. In addition, patients with T1 lesions demonstrated markedly higher creatinine levels compared with T0 lesions [4.01 (1.40–7.45) vs 0.83 (0.70–1.00), $p<0.001$]. Regarding crescent formation, serum creatinine levels were highest in C2 lesions, followed by C1 and C0 lesions [3.60 (1.47–6.85) vs 0.98 (0.70–3.25) vs 0.81 (0.69–0.95), $p=0.008$], as presented in Table 7.

Table (7): Association of renal function with MEST-C classification.

		Blood urea(mg/dl)	Serum creatinine(mg/dl)
Mesangial cellularity (M)	M0	15.0(10.0-37.50)	0.9(0.70-1.75)
	M1	15.65(8.62-40.20)	0.88(0.00-1.22)
P-value		0.954	0.706
Endocapillary hypercellularity (E)	E0	15.90(9.925-47.900)	0.88(.702-3.05)
	E1	15.00(10.00-30.00)	0.91(0.7-1.20)
P-value		0.801	0.893
Segmental sclerosis (S)	S0	12.4(9.35-18.0)	0.81(0.68-0.99)
	S1	28.50(10.92-53.75)	1.04(0.77-4.08)
P-value		0.014*	0.019*
Interstitial fibrosis/tubular atrophy (T)	T0	9.97(9.97-28.25)	0.83(0.70-1.00)
	T1	52.0(23.700-74.00)	4.01(1.40-7.45)
	T2	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)
P-value		0.008*	<0.001*
Cellular or fibrocellular crescents (C)	C0	11.40(8.75-16.60)	0.81(0.69-0.95)
	C1	21.20(10.900-49.000)	0.98(0.70-3.25)
	C2	72.00(35.5-104.75)	3.60(1.47-6.85)
P-value		0.002*	0.008*

*p-value is significant

Median blood urea levels differed significantly according to C3 deposition intensity. Patients with C3 (+2) showed the highest median blood urea level compared with C3 (+1) and negative C3 groups [41.00 (18.0–94.50) vs 12.00 (9.45–21.80) vs 15.80 (12.0–35.0), $p=0.028$], respectively. Median serum creatinine levels also demonstrated significant differences according to C3 and IgM deposition intensity. Higher serum creatinine levels were observed in patients with C3 (+2) compared with C3 (+1) and negative groups [1.50 (0.98–4.80) vs 1.00 (0.68–2.00) vs 0.80 (0.70–0.95), $p=0.008$]. Similarly, patients with IgM (+2) had significantly higher serum creatinine levels than those with IgM (+1) and negative IgM [3.40 (1.09–6.15) vs 0.90 (0.77–1.10) vs 0.80 (0.68–1.00), $p=0.001$]. Patients with combined positive IgM and IgG deposits had

significantly higher median serum creatinine levels compared with negative cases [1.30 (0.90–4.40) vs 0.83 (0.70–1.00) mg/dL, $p=0.029$]. In addition, patients with positive C3 and IgM deposits demonstrated significantly higher median blood urea [52.00 (12.5–94.50) vs 13.05 (9.97–26.5), $p=0.01$] and serum creatinine levels [2.00 (1.04–4.80) vs 0.805 (0.69–0.99) mg/dL, $p<0.001$] compared with negative cases. Furthermore, combined positivity for C3, IgM, and IgG was associated with significantly higher serum creatinine levels [1.40 (0.94–3.80) vs 0.85 (0.70–1.10) mg/dL, $p=0.033$]. Patients with positive C3 and IgG deposits also showed significantly elevated serum creatinine levels compared with negative cases [1.30 (0.90–2.00) vs 0.83 (0.70–1.00) mg/dL, $p=0.049$], as presented in Table 8.

Table (8): Correlation of renal Function with Immunofluorescence Deposition Patterns

		Blood urea (mg/dl)	Serum creatinine(mg/dl)
C1q	0	15.25(10.0-34.25)	0.88(0.70-1.10)
	+1	28.00(4.00)	18.50(2.00)
	+2	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
	+3	59.00	4.01
P-value		0.392	0.062
C3	0	12.00(9.45-21.80)	0.80(0.70-0.95)
	+1	15.8(12.0-35.0)	1.00(0.68-2.00)
	+2	41.00(18.0-94.50)	1.50(0.98-4.80)
	+3	34.00	1.37
P-value		0.028*	0.008*
IgG	0	15.90(9.97-36.70)	0.81(0.70-1.00)
	+1	15.50(11.40-41.00)	1.09(0.81-1.50)
	+2	11.30(8.50-33.75)	2.05(0.60-14.07)
	+3	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
P-value		0.690	0.312
IgA	0	11.85(8.05-18.30)	0.80(0.72-0.89)
	+1	14.75(10.00-49.50)	0.96(0.70-1.92)
	+2	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
	+3	29.00(13.5-52.0)	1.09(0.64-4.15)
P-value		0.07	0.22

IgM	0	15.80(10.50-28.00)	0.80(0.68-1.00)
	+1	13.00(9.70-32.00)	0.90(0.77-1.10)
	+2	41.00(11.8-80.50)	3.40(1.09-6.15)
	+3	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
P-value		0.180	0.001*
IgM & IgG	Negative	15.65(10.0-34.25)	0.83(0.70-1.00)
	Positive	15.00(10.00-52.00)	1.30(0.90-4.40)
P-value		0.81	0.029*
C3 & IgM & IgG	Negative	14.00(10.0-32.00)	0.85(0.70-1.10)
	Positive	35.50(11.25-69.25)	1.4(0.94-3.80)
P-value		0.22	0.033*
C3 & IgM	Negative	13.05 (9.97-26.5)	0.805(0.69-0.99)
	Positive	52.00(12.5-94.50)	2.00(1.04-4.80)
P-value		0.01*	<0.001*
C3 & IgG	Negative	14.75(10.0-34.25)	0.83(0.70-1.00)
	Positive	16.70(10.00-52.00)	1.30(0.90-2.00)
P-value		0.53	0.049*

*p-value is significant

Figure (1) :Mesangial Proliferation with Matrix Expansion, Interstitial Inflammation, and tubular Injury, H and E stain (200x), observed under light microscopy.

Figure (2): IgA Immunofluorescence demonstrating strong (3+) granular mesangial deposits, (200x).

DISCUSSION:

The present study evaluated clinicopathological correlations in 55 patients with IgA nephropathy (IgAN) and demonstrated significant associations between histopathological severity and renal function impairment. A slight male predominance was observed, which is consistent with previous regional and international studies reporting higher frequencies of IgAN among males⁽¹⁷⁻²⁰⁾. However, this finding differs from another Iraqi study that reported a female predominance⁽¹⁹⁾. Variations in sex distribution among studies may be attributed to geographical, genetic, and referral-related differences.

Regarding clinical presentation, most patients had mild-to-moderate proteinuria, while microscopic hematuria was highly prevalent. These findings are comparable to earlier reports demonstrating that sub-nephrotic proteinuria and microscopic hematuria are the most common clinical manifestations of IgAN^(20,21). The relatively low frequency of gross hematuria in the current study compared with previous reports may reflect differences in disease stage at the time of biopsy or variations in patient selection criteria^(20,22,23).

Assessment according to the Oxford MEST-C classification revealed substantial frequencies of endocapillary hypercellularity, segmental sclerosis, and crescents. The presence of these lesions indicates active and chronic glomerular injury and may reflect a higher risk of progressive renal dysfunction. Similar observations were reported in Iraqi and regional studies, although the proportion of lesions varied between cohorts^(20,24).

The variability in MEST-C distribution among studies could be related to differences in disease severity, timing of renal biopsy, and population characteristics. The current study found no significant association between sex, hematuria, or proteinuria and MEST-C scores or immunofluorescence findings. This contrasts with previous studies that reported more severe pathological lesions and renal impairment among male patients^(17,20). Differences in sample size and patient demographics may explain these discrepancies. Despite the absence of significant associations with clinical variables, renal function markers showed strong correlations with histopathological severity. Higher serum creatinine and blood urea levels were observed in patients

with segmental sclerosis, tubular atrophy/interstitial fibrosis, and crescent formation, supporting the prognostic value of the MEST-C classification. Similar findings were documented in earlier studies, where advanced T and S lesions were strongly associated with renal impairment and progression to end-stage renal disease^(20,25-27).

Immunofluorescence findings demonstrated universal IgA deposition with frequent co-deposition of IgM, IgG, and C3. Importantly, patients with stronger C3 and IgM deposition had significantly higher serum creatinine and blood urea levels, indicating worse renal function. These findings support previous evidence suggesting that complement activation and combined immune deposits contribute to more severe renal injury and poorer prognosis in IgAN patients⁽²⁸⁾. Overall, the study highlights the importance of integrating biochemical, histopathological, and immunofluorescence findings for better assessment of disease severity and prognosis in IgAN.

CONCLUSION:

Clinicopathological assessment in IgA nephropathy provides important prognostic information regarding disease severity and renal function impairment. Higher blood urea and serum creatinine levels were significantly associated with advanced Oxford MEST-C lesions, particularly segmental sclerosis, tubular atrophy/interstitial fibrosis, and crescents. Furthermore, stronger and combined immune deposits, especially C3, IgM, and IgG, were linked to poorer renal function, highlighting their potential role as markers of disease progression.

Conflicts of Interest:

No conflicts of interest.

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